

A Study on Customer Expectations and Satisfaction Level towards Online Shopping in Karkala Region

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ABSTRACT

Online shopping is a recent phenomenon in the field of E-business. Companies use the Internet to convey, communicate and disseminate information to sell the product, to take feedback and also to conduct satisfaction surveys with customers. Various researches showed that the customers use the Internet not only to purchase the product online, but also to compare prices, product features and after sale service facilities they will receive if the purchase the product from a particular store. In this context, a study was conducted on Online shopping behaviour in Karkala region, Udupi District. The results of study was that on-line shopping in this region is significantly affected by various Demographic factors like age, gender, marital status, occupation and income. Researchers found that most of the respondents prefer cash on delivery as the most favoured payment method. This study reveals that people in Karkala Region chose Amazon and Flipkart to be their favourite online shopping portal. In addition, the respondents were bothered about security of private data provided by them.

Keywords: Online shopping, preferred, portals, expectation and satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Competing in a high-pressure business scenario has become a challenge for retailers. As an effective alternative sales channel sellers are looking at the internet, which gives them direct access to target customers. Online retailing (also known as e-tail) is a web-enabled interface between a retailer and its target consumers for selling products and services on the web with the facility of ecommerce. These kinds of retailers are also known as e-tailor. Almost all big retailers are now electronically present on the World Wide Web. The online shopping environment has gone through a lot of transformation and today it is still developing in a much diversified way. It has become very popular in the areas of apparel, arts and handicrafts, books, car rentals, computers and electronics, cosmetics, financial services, gifts and novelties, etc. Some of the major advantages of e-retailing which makes it popular among the retailers are: low investment cost, direct access to target customers, quick return on investment. This kind of retail format helps the retailers to serve their customer quickly and more efficiently by offering them a detailed portfolio of products and services. On the other hand, availability of the point of transaction data helps the retailers to analyse and interpret their target customers. It has become the most efficient way to offer valuable information to the customers like discounts, promotions, new and existing products as per the customer requirements and past shopping behaviour. Availability of plenty of information about the products has increased the confidence level among the consumers. The increasing purchasing power of the Indian customers is set to bring online shopping boom in India. One of the latest additions to online retail is advertising through social media websites like Facebook, Twitter, Google+, etc. Apart from website technologies, retail leaders are trying to adopt video, mobile and social media strategies with a view to provide richer, more engaging and user friendly experience.

ONLINE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR:

Everybody in the world is the consumer. Each of us buys and sells or consumes goods and services in life. Consumer behaviour is very complex and is determined to a large extent by social and psychological factors. Consumer behaviour can be defined as those acts of individuals directly involved in obtaining, using and disposing of economic goods and services.

The relevance and importance of understanding consumer behaviour is rooted in modern marketing. The needs of not even two consumers are the same. Therefore they buy only those products and services which satisfy their wants and desires. To survive in the market, a firm has to be constantly innovating and understanding the latest consumer needs and tastes. It will be extremely useful in exploiting marketing opportunities and in meeting the challenges that the Indian market offers.

Online consumer behaviour parallels that of offline consumer behaviour with some obvious differences. The stages of the consumer decision process are basically the same whether the consumer is online or offline. But the general model of

consumer behaviour needs modification to take into account new factors. In the online model, web site features along with consumer skills, product characteristics, attitudes towards online purchasing and perceptions about control over the Web environment play a vital role. There are parallels in the analogue world, where it is well known that consumer behaviour can be influenced by store design, and that understanding the precise movements of consumers through a physical store can enhance sales if goods and promotions are arranged along the most likely consumer tracks.

Consumer skills refer to the knowledge that consumer has about how to conduct online transactions. Some products can be easily described, packaged and shipped over the Internet whereas others cannot. Combined with traditional factors such as brand, advertising and firm capabilities, and these factors lead to specific attitudes about online shopping.

Consumer behaviour regarding the use of internet for shopping varies. Some consumers either lack access or resist using this new channel of distribution, primarily due to privacy and security concerns. Other shoppers choose to browse the Web so as to gather information and then visit the stores to negotiate the purchase face to face with the retailer. Few shoppers visit retail stores first and then buy from an e-tailor. Still others do all the shopping online: gathering information, negotiating, purchasing and either arranging for delivery or picking up the merchandise in the store.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The research has been conducted with the following objectives :

- To study customer behaviour towards online shopping,
- To identify the factors that determines the choice of online shopping portals of customers,
- To determine the popularity and preferred choice of online portals.

III. Scope, Methodology and Limitations:

The increasing reach of the Internet among customers has resulted in more and more retailers providing online avenues for customers to make purchases at the click of the mouse. Customers not only use the internet to make purchases but also to search for information about the product or service being purchased. Internet has changed the way of conducting business. Many businesses have started building up their strategies around the internet.

If E-Marketers analyse and understand the factors influencing customers' online behaviour, they can further fine-tune their business strategies towards customer preferences.

This study deals with the customers' expectations and satisfaction level regarding the Product categories that customers purchase online, Quality & availability of the product, Mode and Speed of delivery of the product, Product price / Offers provided for online shoppers, Payment options available for the customers and Features of the shopping website such as Design, Information provided, Accessibility and Ease of use.

The nature of this research is descriptive as well as exploratory and the goal of this research is to explore the consumer expectations and satisfaction level towards online shopping and to measure how these factors are extensive. For this reason, a survey was conducted in Karkala Region to collect primary data by using structured questionnaire which contains 15 relevant questions regarding online shopping. A convenience random sampling procedure has been used to collect data for this research.

The Information collected during data collection was coded first in MS Excel and tables were generated, analyzed and interpreted. To find out customers satisfaction level towards online shopping, researchers used Mean and Standard deviation as Statistical tools. On the basis of findings based on tabulated information and Observations during data collection, conclusion was drawn.

The present research has few limitations. One limitations among them is that the sample size. The sample size for this research is 50 respondents. Aside from that, this study can also be context specific. The respondents for this research were principally from Karkala Region. This research is limit on the respondent who are purchase goods through online. Future research is advised to increase the sample and should cover other region to increase the validity.

However, the study has limitations in terms of time constraints and the validity of the responses cannot be guaranteed to be true always as it is subject to human perceptions and attitudes which is subject to change often. Thus, the results may not be able to be generalized.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. A.B Santhi (2017), "A study on the customer satisfaction towards online shopping in Tirupathi". This study has been undertaken to understand the factors influencing customer's online shopping decisions and how these factors affect customer satisfaction. The result reflect the perception, preferences, and factors influencing satisfaction of online

shoppers in Tirupathi town. Efforts need to be taken to educate the online buyers on the steps that need to be undertaken while making an online purchase.

M. Rajeshwari (2015), “A study on the customer satisfaction towards online shopping in Chennai city”. As an effective alternative sales channel sellers are looking at the internet, which gives them direct access to target customers. Customers not only use the internet to make purchases but also search for information about the product or service being purchased.

Habibur Rahman and Lili Han (2011), “customer satisfaction in E-commerce: A case study of China and Bangladesh”. The use of the internet is no longer limited to those computer nerds who do it for fun or curiosity. It has opened up tremendous business opportunities for its own use. Since the consumer to business products and services and satisfaction with the enterprise itself is constantly changing, such as the emergence of new technologies, competitors change, and customer needs and expectations change, etc. will lead to changes in customer satisfaction.

Priya A/P Selvaindran (2015), “customer satisfaction towards online shopping for amazon” which reveals that marketers able to improve and re-plan their marketing strategies to make sure to satisfy the customer based on customer expectations. By fulfilling the customer satisfaction, customer will repeat purchasing and it will become bridge between the customer and firms.

Lai Wang Wang and Quoc Liem Le (2015), “customer satisfaction towards online shopping at electronics” reveals that online shopping draws e-services to customer, it establish a new service model for electronic shopping centres and also said that 5 factors will effected on customer satisfaction that is product satisfaction, tangible, empathy, principal to delivery and efficiency to delivery.

Dr. Gopal and Deepika Jindoliya (2016), “customer buying behaviour towards online shopping” it reveals that due to adoption of new marketing strategies, which influence customer to visit the site and make purchases. It gives clear cut data to understand decision making process of consumers.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The data are analyzed based on the questionnaire prepared, the data analysis and interpretation are shown for important questions below.

1. Demographics:

Gender		No. of respondents	%
	MALE	27	54
	FEMALE	23	46
		50	100
Age (in years)		No. of respondents	%
	15 - 20	4	8
	21 -25	15	30
	26 -30	12	24
	31 -35	4	8
	36 -40	8	16
	41 -45	3	6
	46 -50	2	4
	50 and above	2	4
		50	100
Educational Qualification		No. of respondents	%
	SSLC	3	6
	PUC	4	8
	UG	15	30
	PG	24	48
	MPHIL	2	4
	PHD	2	4

		50	100
Occupation		No. of respondents	%
	GOVT EMPLOYEE	9	18
	PRIVATE EMPLOYEE	10	20
	BUSINESS	8	16
	HOUSEWIFE	4	8
	OTHERS	8	16
	STUDENT	11	22
	Total	50	100
Annual income (in Rupees)		No. of respondents	%
	BELOW 120000	25	50
	120000 -300000	9	18
	300000 - 500000	6	12
	500000 AND ABOVE	10	20
	Total	50	100
Marital status		No. of respondents	%
	Married	31	62
	Unmarried	19	38
	Total	50	100

The above table reveals the details about demographics. It is found that the respondents belongs to age group between 18-55 years. Majority of them were Private employees, Government employees and Students. The sample size was limited to 50, out of them 50 % respondents belongs to the group of below 120000 annual income.

2. Preferred choice of shopping portals: 2(a). Clothing:

Gender	Online	Offline	Total
Male	8	19	27
Female	12	11	23
Total	20	30	50

In the above data it is surprising to see that majority of males were preferring offline for clothing and majority of female were preferring online for clothing.

2(b). Mobile phones:

Gender	Online	Offline	Total
Male	20	7	27
Female	10	13	23
Total	30	20	50

In the above it is found that 20 males were preferring online for mobile phones and 13 females prefer offline for mobile phones.

2©. Watches:

Gender	online	Offline	Total
Male	16	11	27
Female	10	13	23
Total	26	24	50

The above table reveals that 16 males prefer online and 13 females prefer offline for watches.

2(d). Electronic Gadgets:

Gender	Online	Offline	Total
Male	6	21	27
Female	3	20	23
Total	9	41	50

In this table it is interpreted that majority of males (21) and females (20) both prefer offline for electronic gadgets.

2(e). Cosmetics

Gender	Online	offline	Total
Male	6	21	27
Female	9	14	23
Total	15	35	50

This table shows that majority of males and female both prefer offline for cosmetics.

2(f). Literary items:

Gender	online	offline	Total
Male	8	19	27
Female	9	14	23
Total	17	33	50

With regards to literary items majority of male and female prefer offline mode than online.

3. Frequency of Visiting online portals:

Occupation	Daily	Weekly	Once in a month	Occasionally	Whenever I need to shop	Total
Govt. employee	1	3	0	2	3	9
Pvt. Employee	1	3	0	2	4	10
Business	2	4	0	0	2	8
Housewife	1	0	0	0	3	4
Others	0	4	0	2	2	8

Students	1	2	0	4	4	11
Total	6	16	0	10	18	50

From the above data it is clear that 6 respondents visit online portals daily, 16 were visiting weekly, no one visits once in a month, 10 were visit occasionally and majority (18) of the respondents visit online portals whenever they need to shop.

4. Payment Method:

Occupation	Cash on delivery	Debit card	Credit card	Net banking	Paytm	Phonepay	Others	Total
Govt. employee	5	0	0	4	0	0	0	9
Pvt. employee	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Business	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	8
Housewife	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	4
Others	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
Students	10	1	0	0	0	0	0	11
Total	40	5	1	4	0	0	0	50

Although there were several online payment modes still majority of respondents prefer cash on delivery as mode of payment while shopping online. Some of them prefer Debit card and Net banking.

5. Expectations of respondents towards online shopping portals: 5(a). Websites must have a clear display:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	1	0	2	11	13	27
Female	0	0	2	13	8	23
Total	1	0	4	24	21	50

Majority of respondents agreed that they expect websites must have clear display.

5(b). The payment procedure should not be complicated:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	1	2	0	15	9	27
Female	0	0	2	16	5	23
Total	1	2	2	31	14	50

Among 50 respondents 31 agrees and 14 were strongly agree that they expect simplicity in payment procedure.

5©. Prices will not matter when shopping online:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	6	15	4	2	0	27
Female	2	11	5	3	2	23
Total	8	26	9	5	2	50

From the above table it is clear that majority (26) were disagree that prices will not matter when shopping online.

5(d). There should be quick delivery:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	6	15	4	2	0	27
Female	0	1	2	14	6	23
	6	16	6	16	6	50

The above data reveals that 16 respondents agree and 16 respondents disagree for the factor there should be quick delivery.

5(e). Discounts and offers:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	1	2	0	14	10	27
Female	0	1	3	11	8	23
Total	1	3	3	25	18	50

This table interprets that 25 respondents were agree and 18 were strongly agree that they look for more discounts and offers.

5(f) Wide variety of choices:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	0	1	2	11	13	27
Female	1	0	0	12	10	23
Total	1	1	2	23	23	50

Here, we found that 23 were agree and 23 were strongly agree that there must be wide variety of choices.

5(g). Private data must be kept confidential:

Gender	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	0	0	3	9	15	27
Female	0	0	1	10	12	23
Total	0	0	4	19	27	50

All the respondents says that the website must maintain confidentiality of private data provided by the customers.

6. Satisfaction level towards online shopping portals: Mean and Standard Deviation:

Factors	No. of respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. Display	50	3.82	0.53
2. Search option	50	3.46	3.19
3. Payment procedure	50	3.88	0.43
4. Delivery timings	50	3.56	0.97

5. Prices offered	50	3.04	1.52
6. Discounts and offers	50	3.36	0.83
7. Variety/choices	50	3.6	1.04
8. Security of private data	50	3.76	0.74
9. Description of the product	50	3.72	0.56

All the above factors are on an average much above the rating scale of neither satisfied nor dissatisfied and not go beyond satisfied. In an average payment procedure is less variable factor and search option is highly variable.

7. Favourite E-commerce shopping portal:

	Amazon	E-bay	Flipkart	Myntra	OLX	Snapdeal	Total
Male	13	0	10	0	2	2	27
Female	16	0	7	0	0	0	23
Total	29	0	17	0	2	2	50

Chart 1:

Based on table 7 and chart 1, we could rank e-commerce shopping portals as first rank to Amazon, second rank to Flipkart followed by OLX and Snapdeal.

FINDINGS

Though usage of online shopping by customers is increased, customers still prefer offline shopping for regular purchase. Majority of customers have used online shopping and shown willingness to continue but very few of them have done online shopping earlier and not showing willingness to continue. Respondents are preferring online shopping due to various motives like less price or price discount, time saving, due to availability of number of sites range and variety of products are available and customers are having choice to purchase, customers found purchase method very easy as websites are user-friendly and customers want to avoid hassles of shopping in store. Majority of respondents are satisfied with online shopping, Customers want to see product in person before buy, Customers are having fear of receiving wrong or bad product and could not return, Customers are worried about giving credit card number, Occupation

of respondent is independent of purchase habit. Occupation is not playing any role in product choice.

Table 4 reveals that majority of respondents were preferring cash on delivery as best payment method.

As per table 2(a), it is surprise to see that majority of Males were preferring offline mode for clothing although generally they were not ready to spend more time for shopping.

The table 3(a),3(b) and 3(e) interprets that majority of respondents visit online portals daily and weekly basis and also found that there were respondents who visit online portals whenever they need to shop.

I can rank the online shopping portals based on the data in Table 7 and Chart 1 as first rank for Amazon and second rank for Flipkart followed by OLX and Snapdeal.

CONCLUSION

An attempt was made by researcher to study the present status of online shopping behaviour in Karkala region. 50 respondents from this place were selected. Opinion from these respondents was collected with the help of well-structured questionnaire. With the help of Data analysis and interpretation finding were drawn by researcher. With the help of findings following conclusion and suggestions were drawn by researcher.

E-commerce shopping portals should make return procedure simpler, like few portals are asking customers to resend products if any wrong or bad product arrived. Instead of these online portals should collect product from customers and deliver right product to them in minimum time.

Most of customers want to see product before purchase to make sure that same product arrived as per order.

From the above discussion, it is concluded that Online shopping give customers best alternative to save money and time. Online shopping portals offers detail product information, easy mode of payment, facility of comparison of price. Success of online shopping depends on its popularity, its brand image and its unique promotional policies.

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